

Contents

Abstract.....	2
Introduction	3
Discussion/literature review	4
Problems <i>at</i> Unsignalized Intersections.....	4
Influence of Gap Acceptance on Safety and Performance of the Intersection	5
Measures to Mitigate Crashes and Accidents at Unsignalized Intersections	6
References	8

Gap Acceptance at Unsignalized Intersections: It's impact on Road Performance and Safety

Abstract

A gap is the time lag between two vehicles or a vehicle and a pedestrian in any roadway facility. Gap acceptance is to either accept or reject the gap in the traffic stream during the merging or crossing with another traffic stream. Gap acceptance is widely used for determination of capacity, delay and level of service at various facilities. Gap acceptance has been recently used to study simulation models and Intelligent Transport Systems (Hwang and Park, 2005). As an unsignalized intersection is one of the most hazardous locations on highway, gap acceptance has a great impact on the performance and safety of the intersection. At any unsignalized intersection, each driver must make their own decision regarding the maneuver, which is impacted by various dynamics like geometric, traffic, environmental and human factors. Road safety is directly associated with the driver's ability to make the decision. This graduate research paper provides a general overview of gap acceptance behavior of drivers on various types of intersections and the impact on the performance and safety of the road. A systematic literature review is carried out and various models developed by researchers will be studied to draw conclusions. The main objective of the paper is to show that gap acceptance behavior of a driver at an unsignalized intersection is affected by various factors and how that has an adverse effect on the safety and performance of the road networks. Also, the ways to mitigate the negative effects will be studied.

Key words: Gap Acceptance, Unsignalized Intersection, Critical gap Road Safety and Performance.

Introduction

Intersections are classified into two categories based on traffic control measures (1) signalized intersections (intersections which are controlled by traffic signals) and (2) unsignalized intersections. Unsignalized intersections are again classified into (a) uncontrolled intersections, (b) STOP sign-controlled intersections, (c) YIELD sign-controlled intersection and (d) Roundabout. These intersections are regarded as a critical location of any road network as conflicts and delays frequently arise during the movement of vehicles or pedestrians. Gap acceptance is a very important traffic characteristics used for analysis of unsignalized intersections. The driver's acceptance or rejection of the existing gap solely depends on his capability to decide and not on any rules or traffic control device which makes it a matter of concern since human behavior is unpredictable and differs from person to person. The decision, however, is influenced by various factors like the driver's age, gender, and experience. Also, different vehicle has different characteristics like speed and dimension and have different response in presence of other vehicles. A critical gap (minimum gap) is used to estimate the safety and capacity at an unsignalized intersection, which is defined as "the minimum gap that all the drivers in the traffic stream are assumed to accept at similar locations". Under heterogeneous traffic conditions, the estimation of critical gap is more complex than homogeneous traffic. Road accidents and crashes are highly affected by the gap acceptance behavior. Different models are formed for the estimation of critical gaps for different road conditions. Poor acceptance of gap is the major reason for crashes at an unsignalized intersection.

A few mathematical approaches for driver's gap acceptance are found due to vehicle interaction complexity. Most of the researchers use empirical methods leading to design and operational

procedures. According to previously conducted studies, the gap acceptance behavior of the driver is strongly related to the attributes of the driver, vehicle, and the road.

Discussion/literature review

Various literatures have been available for the study of gap acceptance, however, most of them are confined to the homogeneous traffic. Bhatt & Shah, (2022) studied the impact of gap acceptance on road safety and did a critical systematic review. Elayan et al (2013) studied the gap acceptance behavior at U turn median openings in Jordan. Karthika P T (2014) studied the gap acceptance behavior of drivers at T- intersections. Dutta and Ahmed (2017) studied the gap acceptance behavior of driver at uncontrolled T-intersections under mixed traffic conditions. Lee et al (2018) studied the evaluation of the rain effects on gap acceptance behavior at roundabout by a logit model. In this paper, different papers on gap acceptance are studied and reviewed to draw conclusions on the gap acceptance behavior at different types of intersections and its impact on road safety.

Problems at Unsignalized Intersections

An unsignalized intersection is a very common area for accidents and crashes. Main reason for the accident is the negligence of the driver. Since the intersection is only controlled by STOP or YIELD, drivers should make their own decision on how to proceed. Finding a suitable gap in the traffic becomes challenging when the volume is high on the major road. The vehicles from the

minor road may accept short gaps due to longer waiting time that leads to crashes. This problem can also be faced by the pedestrians when they try to cross the road. Even at the crossways, where the pedestrians have the state given right-of-way, they must wait for the vehicular traffic to slow down to cross the road. And as the wait time increases, pedestrians tend to accept short gaps for crossing or turning maneuvers, which could be risky and might lead to accidents.

Some drivers are more likely to misjudge the gaps than others. This is because of various factors that affect their judgement. Age being one of the major factors, plays a great role in gap acceptance behavior of the driver regardless of the traffic volume at the unsignalized intersection. Other factors include the type of vehicle. Different vehicle needs different time as per their vehicular characteristics and the speed of the major street traffic. The time might vary from 6.5 seconds for right turning passenger cars to 12 seconds for left turning large trucks. Various other factors like environmental factors: rain, adverse weather etc. influences the driver's perception and reaction leading to poor gap acceptance at the unsignalized intersections.

Influence of Gap Acceptance on Safety and Performance of Intersections

Road accidents are caused due to inappropriate movements of vehicles and other road users. It depends on the critical gap and follow-up time. The critical gap is a variable parameter that changes and is predicted using several models by the researchers. 95% of crashes occur due to the driver's error which might be aggressiveness or over speeding. Poor gap acceptance also lowers the quality of road as it leads to delay and queuing of vehicles in the traffic stream. In an unsignalized intersection, usually the minor road is stop controlled and the major road has the through traffic

which does not stop. Due to this the minor street traffic must stop and wait for their turn to merge in the traffic which leads to delay and forms a queue. The excessive delay time impacts driver's behavior leading to accidents.

Measures to Mitigate Crashes and Accidents at Unsignalized Intersections.

Safety and performance of a road is interrelated because as one improves the other is benefitted from it. The crashes and accidents at an unsignalized intersection can be mitigated by improving the intersection using the Engineering, enforcement and education which is often noted as 3 E's.

Engineering treatments include changing the physical features or design elements of an unsignalized intersection. These treatments include traffic control devices like signs, signals and pavement markings used to warn, regulate or guide traffic, geometric treatments like changing the physical features of the intersection, and installing an intersection light.

Enforcement plays a vital role in mitigating crashes and accidents at an intersection. At an unsignalized intersection motorists and pedestrians violate the rules despite having a good road structure and facility by either making improper turns or failing to come to a full stop under the STOP sign control. The latter one can be enforced by the traditional targeted police enforcement where the police officers position their vehicles so they may view other vehicles approaching the STOP sign.

Another critical component for mitigating crashes at an unsignalized intersection through education. Several educational and awareness programs can be conducted for giving proper information to the public about rules and regulations of the roads. Driver licensing and educational

programs, and targeted education programs focusing on different groups like older drivers, teenagers and children can be conducted. Also, public can be educated through Public Service announcements (PSA) using various media like newspaper and the internet platforms and also by using roadside signs and devices.

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